
Aikido Expert Interviews: a benchmarking study

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Project abstract:

This benchmarking study examines how and to what extent aikido can be useful for intercultural corporate communication training. Aikido, a Japanese martial art, is practised worldwide and aims to turn opponents into partners. Typically, aikido represents the search for harmony, connection and non-violence rather than combat in most other martial arts. In many parts of the world, aikido is also applied as a metaphor or embodied pedagogy for therapy and conflict resolution training. In the field of intercultural business communication training, it can be argued that aikido meets a need for training approaches with experiential discovery rather than conventional didactic expository (Waxin & Panaccio, 2005; Treven, 2003; Graf, 2004; Díaz & Moore, 2018).

We interview twenty aikido experts from around the world to discover what experts consider core principles of aikido today. We record the interviews, transcribe them, pseudonymise the experts' names and, using NVivo software, conduct a qualitative content analysis. The findings show that aikido interactions and intercultural interactions have many similarities. From the analysis, an interaction model for intercultural communication training based on aikido emerges.

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GDPR Record

Collection and processing of personal data

1. Are you collecting or processing personal data?

- Yes

name, e-mail address, town, nationality and gender
pseudonymized

2. In what format are you collecting or processing the personal data?

- Digital
- On paper

Informed consent: on paper and in audio recording
Personal data in the interviews: in audio recording

3. Are you collecting or processing primary personal data and/or secondary personal data?

- Primary personal data

4. If you are processing secondary personal data, will you inform the persons whose personal data are being processed or have they already been informed?

- Yes

5. If no, explain why it is impossible or why it would take a disproportionate effort to inform the persons whose personal data are being processed.

6. How will the personal data be processed?

- Pseudonymised (explain below)

The interviewees agreed to an informed consent and knew that the interviews would be anonymized except for their aikido grade, aikido lineage, nationality, current country of residence and gender. The study uses pseudonyms.

7. If you are going to process personal data in a pseudonymised form, describe the method of pseudonymisation, where you will keep the key, and who has access to it.

The study uses pseudonyms with a Japanese influence: a number and the Japanese *san*-suffix. San can mean both Mr and Ms, both formal and informal, regardless of a person's gender. Moreover, it is common in Japanese to add the san suffix to other nouns and turn them into proper nouns. We thus interviewed One-san, Two-san, Three-san etc.

The key is in an Excel file. The Excel file and the research data are saved on separate University Onedrives.

Categories of personal data & data subjects

8. Are you collecting/processing any of the following special categories of data?

- Data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, or trade union memberships

Nationality

Some participants reveal philosophical or religious beliefs.

9. Which other categories of personal data are you collecting/processing?

- Identification data (names, titles, addresses, phone numbers, passport numbers, IP addresses, cookies, electronic location data (GPS, mobile phone)...))
- Personal characteristics (age, gender, date of birth, marital status, nationality...)
- Leisure activities and interests (hobbies, sports...)
- Education and training
- Occupation and profession
- Audio and video recordings

10. Whose personal data are you collecting/processing?

- Others (please specify below)

Consenting adults

11. Will your research be seriously hampered if the persons whose personal data are being collected/processed exercise their right to access, to rectification, to restriction of processing, to be forgotten, to data portability and/or to object?

- No

12. If yes, please justify the need to deviate from one or more of the rights mentioned in question 11. A justification is required for each deviation.

Purpose(s) of the processing

13. What is/are the purpose(s) of the personal data processing?

The data is processed with the aim of understanding the meaning of aikido, a Japanese martial art, in today's world.

14. What is the legal ground for the processing? If the data are being processed for multiple purposes, you must describe the legal ground for each purpose.

- The research will be performed in the public interest, which means that it will lead to an increase of knowledge and insight to the direct or indirect benefit of society.
- The individuals participating in the research have freely given their explicit consent for the processing of their personal data for one or more specific purposes.

15. If you are processing special categories of personal data (see question 8), on which exception is this based?

- The data subject has given his or her explicit consent.

GDPR responsibility

16. Which institution(s) is/are involved in the research?

- Ghent University

17. Is there another university, hospital, research institute or partner involved in the research (besides Ghent University and/or Ghent University Hospital)?

- No

18. Please specify who determines the purposes ('why') and the means ('how') of the research.

- This is determined within Ghent University: UGent is the data controller.

Data transfers & categories of recipients

19. Are you disclosing/sharing/transferring personal data beyond your project team, either with recipients in UGent or UZ Gent, or with external recipients during or after your research?

- No

20. If yes, to or with which categories of recipients are the personal data being disclosed/shared/transferred?

- Others (please specify below)

n/a

21. If yes, where are the personal data being disclosed/shared/transferred to?

- Belgium

22. What is/are the purpose(s) of the data transfer?

n/a

23. What is the legal ground for the data transfer? If there will be multiple data transfers, you need to indicate the legal ground for each data transfer.

- The transfer will be performed in the public interest, which means that it will lead to an increase of knowledge and insight to the direct or indirect benefit of society.

Retention period

24. What is the envisaged retention period for the different categories of personal data? Please motivate.

- 20 years
- for any further research
- after 20 years it is appropriate to find more recent data

Risk analysis

25. To analyse the possible risks associated with the processing of personal data, please tick the boxes that apply to this research.

- Special categories of personal data are processed in this research (see question 8).

26. Does the research constitute a probable high-risk processing? If you ticked two or more boxes in question 25, the answer is 'yes'.

- No

Security measures

27. What technical and organisational security measures are in place to protect personal data?

- I hereby confirm that I carry out my research in accordance with the guidelines on information security of UGent and/or UZ Gent.

28. If you have motivated the need to deviate from one or more of the rights of the persons whose personal data you are collecting/processing in question 11 and 12, please describe which safeguards are put in place to protect their rights and freedoms.

